

Repurposing Pheophorbide a as an Antiviral Molecule for Human Papillomavirus type 16

Ragıp Soner SİLME^{1*}

Abstract

The emergence of human papillomavirus (HPV) among the human population in different regions of the world has heightened the interest for new treatment methods. Molecular docking is a reliable and predictive method for screening of new potential antiviral molecules against pathogens. The retrieved 42 high-quality whole-genome sequences of HPV were analyzed in search of a stable region which is exist in the genome. The protein encoded by this stable region was targeted for protein-ligand interaction. Consequently, a target constant region which is responsible for encoding the C-terminal domain (monomer) of the HPV45 oncoprotein E7 (PDB: 2ewl) with various regulatory functions for the virus was detected. A ligand "Pheophorbide a ($C_{35}H_{36}N_4O_5$)" interacts with this protein, which could be used against HPV. Pheophorbide a has also been commercially used for cancer treatments due to its anti-proliferative effects and photosensitizer property in photodynamic therapy. This possible antiviral property of Pheophorbide a should be tested on other high-risk and low-risk Papillomaviruses since the E7 oncoprotein also plays a central role in many other HPV types. The predictive results need confirmation with further clinical and *in vitro* studies. The findings will provide new insights into HPV-human cell interactions, induced immunity, and new methods for HPV treatment.

Keywords: Antiviral, Anticancer, HPV, Human papillomavirus, Pheophorbide a.

Feoforbid a'nın İnsan Papilloma Virüsü Tip 16'ya Karşı Kullanımı

Öz

Dünyanın farklı bölgelerindeki insan popülasyonunda insan papillomavirüsünün (HPV) ortaya çıkması, yeni tedavi yöntemlerine olan ilgiyi artırmıştır. Moleküler yerleştirme, patojenlere karşı yeni potansiyel antiviral moleküllerin taranması için güvenilir ve öngörücü bir yöntemdir. Yüksek kaliteli 42 HPV tüm genom dizisi, genomda sabit bir bölgenin varlığı açısından analiz edildi. Bu sabit bölge tarafından kodlanan protein, protein-ligand etkileşimi için analiz edildi. Sonuç olarak, virüs bünyesinde çeşitli düzenleyici işlevlere sahip HPV45 oncoprotein E7'nin C-terminal domaini (monomer) (PDB: 2ewl) proteinini kodlamaktan sorumlu bir sabit bölge tespit edildi. HPV'ye karşı kullanılacak bir ligand olan "Feoforbid a'nın ($C_{35}H_{36}N_4O_5$)" bu proteinle etkileşime girdiği öngörülmüştür. Feoforbid a, fotodinamik terapide anti-proliferatif etkileri ve fotosensitör özelliği nedeniyle ticari olarak kanser tedavilerinde de kullanılmaktadır. Feoforbid a'nın bu kuvvetle muhtemel antiviral özelliği, E7 onkoproteini birçok farklı HPV tipinde de merkezi bir rol oynadığı için, diğer yüksek riskli ve düşük riskli Papillomavirüsler üzerinde test edilmelidir. Bu sonuçların daha ileri klinik ve *in vitro* çalışmalar ile doğrulanması gerekmektedir. Bulgular, HPV-insan hücre etkileşimleri, indüklenen bağışıklık ve HPV tedavisinde geliştirilecek yöntemler konusunda yeni fikirler sağlayabilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Antiviral, Antikanser, HPV, İnsan papilloma virüsü, Feoforbid a.

¹Istanbul University, Center for Research and Practice in Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering, Istanbul, Turkey, rsoner@istanbul.edu.tr

*Sorumlu Yazar/Corresponding Author

1. Introduction

Human papillomaviruses (HPVs) are small, non-enveloped DNA viruses that are ubiquitously present in nature and constitute a diverse viral family, encompassing both benign and highly carcinogenic variants (Van Doorslaer et al., 2018). HPVs primarily replicate within the surface layers of squamous epithelia, particularly at the junctions between squamous epithelial cells and the columnar epithelium of the cervix. This replication can disrupt normal squamous cell proliferation, resulting in abnormal epithelial growth (Leeman et al., 2020). As non-lytic infections, HPVs typically do not provoke a robust immune response or inflammation because they do not activate Toll-like receptors or natural killer cells (Brendle et al., 2014).

To date, > 170 HPV types have been identified, with > 40 of these linked to infections in the female reproductive tract and cervical lesions (Layman et al., 2020). HPV types are divided into high-risk and low-risk groups according to their pathogenic potential. Low-risk types, such as HPV6, HPV11, and HPV30, are associated with benign lesions, including lower-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions and genital warts. In contrast, high-risk strains like HPV16, HPV18, and HPV58 are mainly responsible for causing more severe squamous intraepithelial lesions and cervical cancer (Yang et al., 2020).

In Europe, cervical cancer ranks as the second most common cause of death for young women, with approximately 24,400 deaths reported each year (IARC, 2012). HPV can be present in various anatomical sites, including the genital and urinary tracts, as well as the throat and mouth (Bosch and Muñoz, 2002). Several cofactors have been identified in the development of cervical cancer, including prolonged use of oral contraceptives, sexually transmitted infections, and smoking; however, their influence is considered minor compared with the role of persistent HPV infection (Moscicki et al., 2020). About 43% of vulvar tumors, 70% of vaginal tumors, and 100% of cervical tumors are linked to HPV (Lowy and Schiller, 2012). Although HPV is primarily spread through sexual activity, instances of non-sexual transmission methods, including perinatal vertical transmission and physical contact, have also been documented (Syrjänen and Puranen, 2000).

Some international pharmaceutical companies have developed various HPV vaccines based on virus-like particles derived from the L1 major capsid protein (Brisson et al., 2020). Although these vaccines have become part of government vaccination programmes in over 100 countries (Schiller et al., 2012; Gupta et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2020; WHO, 2022), there are some concerns about their side effects, and their long-term effects are unknown (Brotherton et al., 2008; Sutton et al., 2009; Wildemann et al., 2009; Slade et al., 2009; Mendoza Plasencia et al., 2010; DiMario Jr et al., 2010; Chang et al., 2011; Rossi et al., 2011; Ward et al., 2019; Hineno and Ikeda, 2021). Therefore, new alternative HPV treatment methods are also necessary.

In this study, the unvarying regions of human papillomavirus type 16 were investigated in 42 various genome sequences available in the NCBI database. This study aims to identify stable regions within the viral genome to enable predictions of protein structure and conduct docking analysis to determine a suitable molecule that interacts with this HPV protein to mitigate its virulence (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The flowchart of bioinformatic studies.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Genome Sources

A total of 42 complete HPV type 16 genome sequences were retrieved from the NCBI virus database (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/labs/virus/vssi/#/>) (taxid:333760) as of August 13, 2024. The dataset included only complete genomes with high coverage from geographically diverse countries. The genomes are listed in Table 1 (Supplementary data S1).

2.2. Nucleotide and Amino Acid Sequence Alignment and Analysis

The sequences were examined, and common regions among all genomes were identified based on the results of pairwise alignment using Progressive-MAUVE from the Geneious software (Geneious Prime® 2024.0.7, Biomatters Ltd., Auckland, New Zealand) (Supplementary data S2) (Baysal et al., 2021a).

Every unvarying genomic region was removed from complete sequences and analyzed with the protein similarity programme of the NCBI database via BlastX. The acquired FASTA sequence was transformed into a protein sequence utilizing the ExPASy proteomics server (<https://web.expasy.org/translate/>) (Gasteiger et al., 2003) and then loaded to the I-TASSER (Iterative Threading ASSEmblY Refinement) server of Michigan University, US (<https://zhanglab.ccmb.med.umich.edu/I-TASSER>) for protein prediction (Yang et al., 2015; Baysal et al., 2021a).

2.3. Phylogenetic Analysis

HPV sequences were aligned by using Geneious software (Geneious Prime® 2024.0.7). In order to build phylogenetic tree for the recent genomes, the Tamura-Nei-parameters genetic distance model and the Neighbor-Joining were selected with sorted topologies.

2.4. Homology Modelling and Protein Prediction

The homology models for the target protein, predicted by the ITASSER server system, were obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) (www.rcsb.org) (Table 2). Protein sequences were aligned, and homology modeling was conducted using the ExPASy proteomics server to obtain more structural information (Schwede et al., 2003).

Table 1. The 42 selected whole-genome sequences of human papillomavirus type 16 were used for MAUVE analysis. “-” represents unknown. RefSeq; Reference Sequence. The sequences are listed alphabetically by country of origin.

NCBI Accession Number	Country of Origin	Isolation Source	Bp Length	Collection/Submission Date
K02718.1	-	Human invasive cervical carcinoma	7904	1985/1994
KU053823.1	USA	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	-/2015
HM057182.1	Amazonian-Brazil	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7915	2007/2010
HQ644234.1	Asia	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	-/2010
KP874717.1	Brazil	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7847	-/2015
KU298880.1	Brazil	Cervicovaginal smears	7906	-/2015
KC935953.1	China	Cervical cancer	7906	2012/2013
KF954093.1	China	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7906	2013/2013
MT783409.1	China	Vaginal secretions	7908	2016/2020
MK484705.1	China	Perianal tumor tissue	7912	2018/2019
EU918764.1	China: Gansu province	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7904	2007/2008
MH892050.1	China: Northeast region	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	2017/2018
MW320358.1	China: Northeast region	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7909	2017/2020
FJ006723.1	China: Xinjiang province	Uyгур cervical cancer patient	7963	2006/2008
JN565302.1	Croatia	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7973	2001/2011
AF534061.1	East Asia	Cervicovaginal Cells	7905	-/2002
EU118173.1	Germany	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7906	-/2007
KY883659.1	India	Cervical specimen	7906	2016/2017
KU684311.1	India	Cervical carcinoma	7916	2011/2016
LC511105.1	Japan	Invasive cervical cancer	7688	-/2019
LC456180.1	Japan	Cervix	7904	-/2019
LC193821.1	Japan	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	-/2016
LC368952.1	Japan	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	-/2018
LC718895.1	Japan	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	2021/2022
LC786753.1	Japan	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	2021/2023
AB889488.1	Japan	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7906	-/2013
LC647437.1	Japan	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7906	-/2021
LR861897.1	Luxembourg	Cervical swap	7906	2015/2020
MN961210.1	Mexico	Cervical brushing for liquid-based cytology	7908	-/2020
KX947269.1	Nepal	Cervical samples	7906	2014/2016
KY549156.1	Netherlands	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	2008/2017
OQ911727.1	Pakistan	Oropharynx from patient with head and neck squamous cell carcinoma	7171	2017/2023
OP971046.1	South Africa	Vaginal secretion	7886	2017/2022
KY994539.1	Sweden	Tonsillar carcinoma	7904	2014/2017
KF880690.1	Sweden	Tonsillar carcinoma	7906	2011/2013
FJ610146.1	Thailand	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7906	2008/2009
JQ004092.1	Thailand	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7911	2010/2011
OP711986.1	Togo	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7904	2017/2022
OP751552.1	United Kingdom	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7908	2016/2022
AF125673.1	USA	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7904	1995/1999
AY686579.1	USA	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7906	-/2004
NC_001526.4 (RefSeq)	USA	Invasive cervical carcinoma	7906	1985/2000

2.5. Ligand Retrieval

The structure of Pheophorbide a ($C_{35}H_{36}N_4O_5$) was retrieved from the PubChem database (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>). The docking calculations were performed using this structure. The ligand's 3D structure was subsequently obtained from the PubChem Compound database in SDF format. The ligand parameters were analyzed using the PRODRG online server

(<http://prodrgr2.dyndns.org/cgi-bin/prodrgr.cgi>) (Schüttelkopf and Van Aalten, 2004). The shape complementarity principle was applied with clustering RMSD 4.0 for docking calculations.

2.6. Molecular Docking Studies

Homology modelling and protein prediction analysis have directed us to test the gene responsible for C-terminal domain (monomer) of the HPV45 oncoprotein E7 (PDB: 2ew1), with the ligand. The flexible docking study was conducted using AutoDock v 4.0 (Trott and Olson, 2010). The interaction analysis of protein-ligand complexes and their amino acid positions with bond distances were calculated and visualized using PyMol. Molecular docking simulation results were also confirmed using the protein dock server SWISSDOCK (<http://www.swissdock.ch/docking>) within protein receptors and ligand interactions (Grosdidier et al., 2011). Pymol software was used to gain insight into their all-binding preferences within the active site of the receptor.

Table 2. Homology modelling of the C-terminal domain of the HPV45 oncoprotein E7 using ITASSER (<https://zhanglab.ccmb.med.umich.edu/I-TASSER>) considering the specific sequence. *The highest PDB hit was 2ew1A.

Rank	PDB Hit	Identity 1	Identity 2	Coverage	Norm. Z-score
1*	2ew1A	0.37	0.24	0.55	1.25
2	7evaC	0.07	0.13	0.89	0.76
3	2ew1	0.38	0.24	0.57	5.09
4	2ew1	0.38	0.24	0.57	3.50
5	2ew1A	0.36	0.24	0.56	2.79
6	2ew1	0.38	0.24	0.53	5.26
7	2ew1A	0.38	0.24	0.57	1.13
8	2ew1A	0.38	0.24	0.57	2.29
9	8fw5G	0.11	0.24	0.96	0.52
10	2f8bA	0.38	0.24	0.57	2.35

3. Findings and Discussion

3.1. Nucleotide and Amino Acid Sequence Alignment and Analysis

Our findings indicated significant mutational alterations across the entire genomes, except for the segment between 100 to 850 bp, which remains a consistently stable region within the whole sequences (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Progressive MAUVE analysis presented a stable region shown in light green-yellow (marked with red arrow) among all HPV genomes.

3.2. Phylogenetic Tree

The phylogenetic tree based on maximum likelihood reveals two primary clades; one branch with 5 sequences (Figure 3-a) and another branch with 37 sequences (Figure 3-b) with several clusters. Only within b group there is geographically similar within 15 sequences which belong to Asian countries (Figure 3-b1). The rest of viral genome sequences exhibited geographical difference and distributed in phylogenetic tree. Figure 3 presents the genetic diversity of HPV 16 sequences from geographically diverse countries of the world.

Figure 3. The phylogenetic tree of HPV represents 2 main branches, labeled as (a) and (b). Geographic comparison results show two groups among (b): (b1) genomes sequences from Asian countries and (b2) various sequences from different countries. Group (a) also includes geographically diverse countries.

3.3. Homology Modelling and Protein Prediction

The aligned sequences of the excised uniform regions displayed that the 750-bp fragment contained the C-terminal domain of the HPV45 oncoprotein E7, featuring consistently unvarying sequences (Figure 2). These stable sequences were selected as a template for further protein structural predictions (Figure 2). The results of the submitted sequence converted to amino acid sequence using the ExPASy proteomics server (<https://web.expasy.org/translate>) were structurally very close to the C-terminal domain of the HPV45 oncoprotein E7 (www.rcsb.org/structure/2ewl) (Ohlenschläger et al., 2006) as a target protein according to I-TASSER analysis, and its ligand was determined as Chlorophyll a. Pheophorbide a ($C_{35}H_{36}N_4O_5$), a small molecule, and Chlorophyll a derivative, which is commercially produced and widely used for anticancer studies, was selected as a ligand for molecular docking analysis (Supplementary data S3-S4).

3.4. Molecular Docking Studies

For docking analysis of Pheophorbide a with the C-terminal domain of the HPV45 oncoprotein E7 (PDB: 2ewl), the ligand structure of Pheophorbide a retrieved from the PubChem database, was analyzed (Figure 2, 4, 5). The docking of the HPV45 oncoprotein E7 with the target molecule Pheophorbide a was examined concerning the following factors: (a) amino acids that interact and (b) atoms of the ligand and protein that participate in hydrogen bonding. The SWISSDOCK server results confirmed the outputs obtained from AutoDock software calculations (Figure 5) Clustering histogram of protein and ligand interaction was given in table 3. Number of multi-member conformational clusters found 3 (1, 2 and 7), out of 15 runs (Supplementary data S3-S4).

Table 3. Clustering histogram of protein-ligand interaction. The lowest binding energy was found -7.17 kcal/mol which shows higher interaction between HPV45 oncoprotein E7 and Pheophorbide a.

Cluster Rank	Lowest Binding Energy	Run	Mean Binding Energy	Number in Clusters	Histogram						
					5	10	15	20	25	30	35
					:	1	:	1	:	1	:
1	-7.17	10	-6.23	4	#####						
2	-6.75	6	-6.00	4	#####						
3	-6.56	4	-6.56	1	#						
4	-6.35	7	-6.35	1	#						
5	-5.77	3	-5.77	1	#						
6	-5.45	15	-5.45	1	#						
7	-5.29	11	-5.18	2	##						
8	-5.25	14	-5.25	1	#						

MHGDTPTLHEYMLDLQPETTDLYCYEQLNDSSE
 EEDEIDGPAGQAEPDRAHYNIVTFCCKCDSTLRL
 CVQSTHVDIRTLEDLLMGTLGIVCPICSQKP

Figure 4. The results of submitted sequence were converted to amino acid sequence using the ExPASy proteomics server (<https://web.expasy.org/translate>) for structural analysis using the I-TASSER server.

Figure 5. Visualization depicts docking analysis of Pheophorbide a binding with crystal structure of HPV45 oncoprotein E7 (PDB: 2ew1) (A) hydrophobicity surface 3D representation (B) interaction of Pheophorbide a with HPV45 oncoprotein E7 (C) visualization of hydrogen bond (D) visualization of hydrophobic interaction (E) 2D representation describes the bindings of Pheophorbide a with the active site of HPV45 oncoprotein E7.

Papillomaviruses constitute a diverse group of DNA viruses characterized by circular, double-stranded DNA genomes approximately 8 kilobases (kb) that are organized into three general regions. The upstream regulatory region (URR) contains sequences crucial for control of transcriptional and replicative processes. The early region encodes genes such as *E6*, *E7*, *E1*, *E2*, *E4*, and *E5*, which primarily contribute to enzymatic functions. The structural region encodes the *L1* capsid protein and *L2*, which plays a role in viral DNA packaging. HPVs are categorized according to the genetic similarity of their genomes, with new HPV types recognized as those whose *L1* open reading frame shows less than 90% similarity to established types. So far, more than 90 HPV genotypes have been completely characterized (de Villiers et al., 2004; Layman et al., 2020). Intratypic variants and subtypes are defined as HPVs that differ by less than 10% in their *L1* DNA sequences (Bernard and Apt, 1994; de Villiers et al., 2004). HPVs play a causal role in the development of cervical cancer (CC) and its precursor lesions (IARC, 1995; Clifford et al., 2003a; 2003b; Muñoz et al., 2003). Among the high-risk HPV types linked to cervical cancer, HPV16 is the most prevalent, being detected in approximately 50% of CC cases (Bosch et al., 1995; Muñoz et al., 2003). Multiple variants of HPV16 have been identified across diverse geographic regions and ethnic groups (Ho et al., 1991; Icenogle et al., 1991; Yamada et al., 1997; Picconi et al., 2003). Despite their genetic similarity, five distinct phylogenetic branches of HPV16 variants have been classified based on geographic origin: European, Asian, Asian-American, African-1, and African-2 (Chan et al., 1992; Ho et al., 1993). Subsequent sequence analyses of additional genomic regions, such as *E6*, *L2*, and *L1* have further refined and supported this phylogenetic framework (Yamada et al., 1995). In this study, phylogenetic analysis revealed two primary branches, denoted as (a) and (b). Within branch (b), two subgroups were identified, of which only subgroup (b1) demonstrated geographic alignment with Asian countries (Figure 3).

Although HPV16 variants have been extensively studied in the context of phylogenetics, with detailed descriptions of molecular variations in the *E2*, *L2*, *L1*, URR, and especially the *E6* region (Giannoudis et al., 2001), genetic variation stability of genes within the same lineage or isolate has received limited attention. Giannoudis et al. (2001) has indicated that HPV16 variants exhibit notable differences in biological properties *in vitro*, which may contribute to variations in pathogenicity, carcinogenic potential, and possibly immunogenicity. Additionally, specific HPV16 variants are linked to varying risks of cervical cancer development (Xi et al., 1997; Villa et al., 2000; Berumen et al., 2001; Hildesheim et al., 2001). Recent studies have highlighted the presence of diversifying selection in the *E6* and *E7* oncogenes (DeFilippis et al., 2002), yet the evolutionary processes affecting the whole genome, the coevolutionary relationships between various HPV16 genes, and their biological consequences are still not fully understood.

Among the evolutionary basis of the entire genome, some genes emerge as the sole segment displaying a uniform sequence, distinct from the remaining portion of the genome. The proteins encoded by these regions could be considered as a target point for the purpose of targeted drug design, as described in “*Baysal’s hypothesis*” (Silme, 2024), and the results from previous studies also confirmed this hypothesis (Baysal et al., 2021a; b; Baysal and Silme, 2021; Abdul Ghafoor et al., 2024).

The conserved region of HPV 16 which was determined to be responsible for coding the C-terminal domain (monomer) of the HPV45 oncoprotein E7 through Progressive-MAUVE analysis in this study. HR-HPVs encode three oncogenes, *E5*, *E6*, and *E7* (Münger et al., 1989; Leechanachai et al., 1992), and among these, *E7* appears to be the main driver of cervical carcinogenesis (Riley et al., 2003). The E7 oncoprotein is primarily recognized for its interaction with and degradation of the pRb tumor suppressor protein (Münger et al., 2001). It also associates with other cellular proteins involved in cell cycle regulation, transcriptional repression, and tumor suppression (Münger et al., 2001; Avvakumov et al., 2003; Bernat et al., 2003). In murine models, the combination of HPV16 E7 and exogenous estrogen has been shown to be sufficient to induce high-grade cervical dysplasia and cervical cancer (Herber et al., 1996; Riley et al., 2003; Chung et al., 2008), while causing significant alterations in the expression of numerous cellular genes (Cortés-Malagón et al., 2013). Moreover, sustained expression of fully functional viral oncoproteins E6 and E7 is essential for maintaining extrachromosomal forms of HPV DNA (Thomas et al., 1999). These oncoproteins contribute to creating a cellular environment favorable for HPV persistence by circumventing cellular checkpoints that would otherwise hinder the long-term retention of extrachromosomal DNA (Thomas et al., 1999; Howley and Lowy, 2001; Garner-Hamrick et al., 2004). Viral oncogenes have the capacity to disrupt cell-cycle control checkpoints by interfering with the regulatory mechanisms of cyclins, cyclin-dependent kinases (CDKs), and CDK inhibitors (Zerfass-Thome et al., 1996; Funk et al., 1997; Jones et al., 1997).

This study exhibited the molecule that interacts with E7 protein is Chlorophyll a and Pheophorbide a. These molecules could suppress the E7 oncoprotein, resulting in dysfunction of HPVs’ replication machinery. Previous studies have shown that various HPV subtypes can coexist within the same tissue in clinical specimens, implying that co-infection occurrences may be relatively common (Kulmala et al., 2006). Since the E7 oncoprotein also plays a central role in many other HPV types, this possible antiviral property of Pheophorbide a should be tested on other high-risk and low-risk Papillomaviruses.

Chlorophylls are prominent bioactive compounds known for their significant health benefits, including anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer properties (Ferruzzi and Blakeslee, 2007; Tagauov et al., 2023). Chlorophylls have several beneficial effects, one of which is their strong antioxidant properties

that help reduce oxidative damage to DNA and lipid peroxidation by lowering reactive oxygen species levels and chelating metal ions (Shelton and Vincent, 1963; Pangestuti and Kim, 2011; Hsu et al., 2013; Tagauov et al., 2023). Notably, Chlorophyll a and its metabolites accumulate in specific tissues, such as the liver and gut, suggesting that these organs could be particularly influenced by their positive biological activity (Szczygiel et al., 2008; Xodo et al., 2012).

The chemical nature of porphyrin allows Chlorophylls to function as hydrogen donors, stopping the oxidative chain reaction (Endo et al., 1985). Pheophorbide a is a derivative of Chlorophyll a (Chen et al., 2009). Interestingly, the porphyrin structure of these two molecules and human blood cell hemoglobin are similar (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Chemical structure comparison of Heme, Chlorophyll a and Pheophorbide a.

Previous studies have indicated that Pheophorbide a could induce significant anti-proliferative effects in several human cancer cell lines (Chen et al., 2009; Yoon et al., 2014; Saide et al., 2020), and is used as a photosensitizer in photodynamic therapy (Roeder et al., 1990; Busch et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2014). These studies combined with the results of present study suggest that Pheophorbide a could be a promising candidate for treatment of HPV 16.

Pheophorbide may be produced through the breakdown of consumed plant material (Saide et al., 2020). It has been found that mitochondria from both worms (*Caenorhabditis elegans*) and mice can utilize this molecule through a process known as ad hoc photoheterotrophy (Xu et al., 2014). The metabolic production of this substance in human body should be studied in further studies to understand its possible stimulating effect on the immune system.

In addition to cervical cancers, anogenital, head, and neck cancers are also strongly associated with HPV infection (Brianti et al., 2017; Egawa, 2023). A recent study by Kim et al. (2022) identified Pheophorbide a in *Eupatorium perfoliatum* extract as a novel lymphatic vascular activator that is crucial for maintaining tissue fluid homeostasis and immune surveillance. As shown in figure 6, Pheophorbide a has a similar structure to that of human blood hemoglobin and it not only could stop the replication cycle of HPV but also influence the lymphatic system to stop metastasis that could result in other types of cancer. Further studies are required to understand and confirm its mechanisms of action.

As mentioned above, Pheophorbide a is a derivative of chlorophyll a (Chen et al., 2009; Saide et al., 2020). Chlorophylls are natural pigments commonly found in the human diet, and gaining prominence due to the consumers' increasing preference for natural and health-conscious lifestyle choices. These studies mentioned in the discussion lead us to a quote by Linus Pauling; "*You can trace every sickness, every disease and every ailment to a mineral deficiency*". From this perspective, this statement can be generalized to deficiency of nutritional elements, vitamins and their derivatives, which is complimentary with the "*food as medicine*" philosophy of Hippocrates (Lucock, 2004). The results of this study and previous studies (WHO, 1990; 2003; Baysal and Silme, 2021; Baysal et al., 2021a; 2021b; 2024; Abdul Ghafoor et al., 2024; Silme, 2024) also suggest the feasibility of this approach. Further studies combined with genomics and pharmaceutical techniques on various diseases could widen our understanding of nutritional medicine that states the interconnectedness of human health and the nutrition.

4. Conclusion and Recommendation

This study identified a stable region in the HPV genome, specifically the HPV45 oncoprotein E7, which plays a critical regulatory role in the virus. The molecular docking analysis highlighted Pheophorbide a ($C_{35}H_{36}N_4O_5$) as a potential antiviral molecule that could interact with this target protein, suggesting its possible use in HPV treatment. Given that Pheophorbide a is already used in cancer therapies, its application in HPV treatment represents a promising avenue for future research. Further clinical and *in vitro* validation of these findings could yield valuable insights into human cell-HPV interactions and provide us a new tool for HPV treatments.

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Authors' Contributions

The author has completed the article alone.

Statement of Conflicts of Interest

The author has no conflict of interest to declare.

Statement of Research and Publication Ethics

The author declares that this study complies with Research and Publication Ethics.

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